

Employees' Satisfaction Assessment Based on Fuzzy Logic: A case study of Bandar Abbas Oil Refining Company

Hamid reza Khazaki ^a *

^aProductivity & Quality Engineering Department of Bandar Abbas oil refining company, Bandar Abbas 79145/3184, Iran

Abstract

Employees satisfaction is a pre-condition for increasing productivity and attention to it is a success factor for excellent organizations. This paper presents a new approach for employees satisfaction assessment (ESA) based on fuzzy logic. In the process of ESA there is an element of vagueness or fuzziness associated with inputs that they are language terms. Also, it can be helpful for management having a model to prioritize dissatisfaction key factors according to satisfaction level and weight factors, simultaneously. A fuzzy expert system to deal with this problem is obtained from this research. The suggested model is coded in c-sharp language and implemented in Bandar abbas Oil Refining Company. Experimental results show the increased accuracy, optimize time consuming and better resource concentration in direct of removing dissatisfaction key factors.

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1. Introduction

Employees come to working places to realize some objectives. They get job satisfaction to the extent that they realize these goals and reach their targets. Their job satisfaction decreases to the extent that they dissociate themselves from their objectives and their commitment to the institution decrease (Altinoz et al., 2012).

To meet the corporate needs of the employees, to find job satisfaction in short, it is necessary to take measures to strengthen the feelings of job security, adequate wages, promotion opportunities, the opportunity to show themselves and institutional justice and organizational commitment (Chang et al., 2010).

Since satisfaction subject contains intangibility, imprecision and vagueness, it makes people more difficult to measure employee satisfaction level. To explore the past related research document, most of the methods for evaluating employee satisfaction applies statistics method. 5-point of Likert Scales is the major way to evaluate employee satisfaction in the past. Nowadays, the fuzzy set theory has been applied to the field of management science, like decision making (Hutchinson, 1998; Viswanathan, 1999; Xia et al., 2000), however, it is scarcely used in the field of satisfaction assessment.

Lingual expression, for example, satisfied, fair, dissatisfied, are regarded as the natural representation of the preference or judgment. These characteristics indicate the applicability of fuzzy set theory in capturing the decision makers' preference structure. Fuzzy set theory aids in measuring the ambiguity of concepts that are associated with human being's subject judgment. Since the evaluation is resulted from the different evaluator's view of linguistic variables, its evaluation must therefore be conducted in an uncertain, fuzzy environment. During the process of evaluators are imprecise with two large an allowance for error. Therefore, this study includes fuzzy logic to strengthen the comprehensiveness and reasonableness of the measuring satisfaction level and prioritizing dissatisfaction key factors.

2. Measuring satisfaction level

Job satisfaction is a positive mood resulting from the evaluation of the works and work experiences of the employees (Brief, 1998). Satisfaction is a good measure to evaluate personal attitude to the professional activity of

* "Corresponding author (*)". Tel.: +989173078634
E-mail address: h.khazaki@gmail.com

enterprises. It also expresses a level of happiness of a person in his professional environment connected with interpersonal relations with colleagues and superiors.

The traditional mathematics, including the set theory is not realistically able to describe some problems such as employee satisfaction. For instance, satisfaction level of an individual employee can be described as high instead of an exact number. Fuzzy set theory was introduced by Zadeh (1965 & 1975) to deal with vague, imprecise and uncertain problems. Based on fuzzy logic, employees can select one of the language terms on each factor. As show in Fig 1 triangular membership functions are considered for these language variables. According to fuzzy mathematic, we can calculate average of a fuzzy variable by Eq. (1).

$$s_i = \frac{1}{q} \sum_{k=1}^q s_{ik} = \frac{1}{q} (L_{Si}, M_{Si}, U_{Si}) \quad (1)$$

Where S_i is the satisfaction of factor i and s_{ik} is satisfaction of employee k over factor i and q is the number of employees. Also, LS , MS and US are lower, medium and upper bound of fuzzy linguistic variable, respectively.

As you can see, this average is fuzzy number and it is necessary that nonfuzzy method employed to convert fuzzy number into crisp real number. Center-of-Area method is the most common approach for this purpose Zhao & Govind (1991), and so, defuzzified value of fuzzy number can be obtained from Eq. (2).

$$N_{Si} = \frac{US_i - LS_i + MS_i - LS_i}{3} \quad (2)$$

Finally, total satisfaction calculate by Eq. (3).

$$TS = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i * S_i \quad (3)$$

Where TS is total satisfaction and w_i is the weight (importance) of factor i

Fig1. Triangular membership functions for satisfaction level

In this paper, factor's weight obtained by AHP method, for detail information about this method you can refer to Saaty (1980).

3. Identifying and prioritizing dissatisfaction key factors

Since time and resources are scarce, identifying and prioritizing dissatisfaction key factors is essential. But there is a kind of vagueness or fuzziness associated with input variables that they are language terms. In fact, employees are not able to express their satisfaction or dissatisfaction level with crisp and precise scores. Therefore, if you are to extract rules of prioritizing, need to apply a technique to model linguistic rules and imprecise data. As shown later, one of these techniques is if-then fuzzy rule.

These rules comprise the knowledge base of the fuzzy inference module. A single fuzzy if-then rule assumes the form: If x is A then y is B ,

Where A and B are linguistic values defined by fuzzy sets on the ranges (universes of discourse) x and y , respectively. The if-part of the rule “ x is A ” is called the antecedent or premise, while the then-part of the rule “ y is B ” is called the consequent or conclusion. It must be noted that the antecedent is an interpretation that returns a single number between 0 and 1, whereas the consequent is an assignment that assigns the entire fuzzy set B to the output variable y . All the rules that have any truth in their antecedent will “fire” and contribute to the fuzzy conclusion set. If the antecedent is true to some degree of membership, the consequent is also true to that same degree. This point leads a natural way to combine multiple qualitative assessments (Zafiroopoulos & Dialynas, 2005).

The fuzzy inference uses the method of min–max implication–aggregation inference (Mamdani, 1974). The defuzzification of the output is made using the center of area method. The process of fuzzification, inference and defuzzification is demonstrated in Fig. 2 by using a generic example with two inputs and a single output. Two rules (1–2) are fired applying six membership functions (A_1 – A_2 , B_1 – B_2 , C_1 – C_2). The process has the following five stages where the inputs are x and y (x and y are crisp values):

(1) Fuzzification of inputs:

- Fuzzification of the variables in rule 1 results in: $A_1(x)$, $B_1(y)$;
- Fuzzification of the variables in rule 2 results in: $A_2(x)$, $B_2(y)$;

(2) Application of fuzzy operation (and = min, or = max):

- Fuzzy operation for rule 1 is: $\min(A_1(x), B_1(y))$;
- Fuzzy operation for rule 2 is: $\min(A_2(x), B_2(y))$;

(3) Application of implication method (min):

- Implication for rule 1 is: $C_1 = \min(C_1(\min(A_1(x), B_1(y))))$;
- Implication for rule 2 is: $C_2 = \min(C_2(\min(A_2(x), B_2(y))))$;

(4) Application of aggregation method (max):

The result of the aggregation method is the area $E = \max(C_1, C_2)$

(5) Application of defuzzification (the Center of the Area COA). The result of the defuzzification is the Center of the Area E which is calculated as:

$$C = xE(x)E(x)$$

In this paper, a fuzzy system has been applied for prioritizing dissatisfaction key factors. This work is more important for company with limited resources that they must be prioritized. To prioritize, we considered two as input variables and one as output. These input criteria are satisfaction level and weight (importance of factors) as well as output variable is priority degree.

Fig2. Generic example of fuzzy inference process (Mamdani, 1974)

The first step in this process (using fuzzy rules) is fuzzification of the variables. In this step, the variables are changed to linguistic variables and Membership functions are determined from experts' point of views about type of the variables (Fig 1 & Figs 3-4)

Using direct approach and based on experts explanations about variables, triangular membership functions are used to represent the fuzzy variables. The overlaps between adjacent membership functions allow for a smooth interpolation of the inputs across membership functions. This approach is more qualitative, flexible and interactive in respect of indirect approach that rules are extracted from data via tools like clustering, neural network. Furthermore, the qualitative assessment of the variable type can be expressed more effectively.

In Fig 3, for determining the medium, high and very high pick, at first the average of weights is calculated to medium pick. Then the maximum value of weights is considered to very high pick and finally the mean of these two values will be the high pick.

Based on values depicted in Figs a fuzzy rule base was developed that include rules such:

If (Satisfaction level is Absolute Low) and (Importance of Factor is Very High) then (Priority Degree is Absolute Necessary). There are 18 similar rules that shown in table 1.

Fig3. Triangular membership functions for weight variable

Fig4. Triangular membership functions for priority degree

Table 1. If-then rules

Satisfaction Level	Importance of Factors		
	Very High	High	Medium
Absolute Low	Absolute Necessary	Absolute Necessary	Necessary
Very Low	Absolute Necessary	Necessary	Necessary
Low	Necessary	Necessary	Very High
A Little Low	Very High	Very High	Moderately High
Medium	Moderately High	Moderately High	High
A Little High	High	High	Moderate

4. Case Study

Bandar Abbas oil refining company is branched of National Iranian Oil Company (NIOC). It is located in a site 700-hectar area, 6km north of Persian gulf and 30 km west the city of Bandar Abbas. The main products of company include: gasoline, kerosene, gasoil, fuel oil, jet fuel, liquefied petroleum gas, sulfur and bitumen.

About 1200 people are working in this company. The most of them are graduated in the university. Almost, all employees and their families live in a place near the Bandar abbas city, calls Morvarid town. This town is a company's property and there is a lot of services like treatment center, school, sport complex and restaurant. Measuring satisfaction level of these services and other factors in the company are important for the top management. In recent years, some employees prefer to leave Bandar abbas and work in another companies of NIOC. so, transmit requests have increased exponentially.

This study started in Bandar abbas oil refining company and proposal approach applied in 2012. Structured questionnaires were distributed to 500 employees and 432 valid questionnaires returned. By Cochran method the sample size was 300 with %95 confident.

The measurement instrument was thoroughly evaluated by human resource group of the company. The instrument was developed by multi-dimensional scales to capture satisfaction level by providing respondents with 9-point language variables (Fig 1). the reliability of the survey calculated about %98.8 by Cronbach alpha method.

According to proposal method that explained above, dissatisfaction key factors are identified and prioritized in 2012 year and the process have continued till now. Result for 2012 year have showed in table 2.

For example, item 2 has a little low and medium satisfaction level with 0.66 and 0.34 membership respectively (see Fig 1), and the weight of this factor is 2.2, that is belong to medium and high with 0.44 and 0.56 membership respectively (see Fig 3). So, according to rule base (table 1) and application of implication method (min), the result is:

Table 2. Prioritized key satisfaction key factors of Bandar abbas oil refining company

Item	Factor	Weight (%)	Satisfaction Level	Si (%)	Priority Degree
1	Payback treatment costs process	2.2	A little low (0.75) Medium (0.25)	42.44	6.251
2	Variety of specialist in treatment center of Morvarid town	2.2	A little low (0.66) Medium (0.34)	43.36	6.164
3	Balancing of usual living costs and income	3.5	A little low (0.07) Medium (0.93)	49.29	6.071
4	Transmit illness to other treatment centers if necessary	2.2	A little low (0.39) Medium (0.61)	46.13	5.959
5	Effective loan to solve employee’s problems	3.5	Medium (0.95) A little high (0.05)	50.55	5.946
6	Qualified maintenance on organization’s houses	2.2	A little low (0.12) Medium (0.88)	48.83	5.708
7	Appropriate training courses according to job requirements	2.6	Medium (0.54) A little high (0.46)	54.64	5.536
8	Use employee experiments and applied them to enable other employees	2.6	Medium (0.51) A little high (0.49)	54.88	5.512
9	Effective training courses in direct of developing employee’s talents	2.6	Medium (0.47) A little high (0.53)	55.26	5.474
10	Qualified food and services in refinery restaurant	2.2	Medium (0.92) A little high (0.08)	50.85	5.434
11	Refer illnesses to Bandar abbas specialist, if necessary	2.2	Medium (0.74) A little high (0.26)	52.59	5.237
12	Sufficient control on environment pollutions resulting from production process	1.9	Medium (0.96) A little high (0.04)	50.376	5.177

- Rule1: if satisfaction level is a little low (0.66) and weight is medium (0.44) then, priority is M-high (0.44).
- Rule2: if satisfaction level is a little low (0.66) and weight is high (0.56) then, priority is V-high (0.56).
- Rule3: if satisfaction level is medium (0.34) and weight is medium (0.44) then, priority is high (0.34).
- Rule4: if satisfaction level is medium (0.34) and weight is high (0.56) then, priority is M-high (0.34).

With application of aggregation method (max), the final fuzzy result is M-high (0.44), V-high (0.56) and high (0.34). so by defuzzified method the priority number calculate:

$$\text{Priority Degree} = (5*0.34+6*0.44+7*0.56) / (0.34+0.44+0.56) = 6.164$$

5. Conclusion

It has been widely accepted that the issue of employee satisfaction is important for the success of the organization. Several models and methods with different mathematical tools are used to evaluate employee satisfaction. Also, identifying and prioritizing of dissatisfaction key factors for human resource management regarded to scarce resources in organizations is essential.

As mentioned earlier, when we refer to satisfaction assessment, special difficulties arise from the fact that some data are insufficiently precise or uncertain. We may conclude that fuzzy logic provide very convenient tools for analyzing and understanding procedures of decision making under uncertainty and vagueness. In traditional investigative research, statistics and mainly 5-point of Likert Scales used for capturing employees’ satisfaction level. The approach suggested in this paper gives a possible solution to employee satisfaction assessment problems in the area of measuring satisfaction level and prioritizing dissatisfaction key factors. In this paper fuzzy language variables used for measuring satisfaction and then a fuzzy expert system established for identifying and prioritizing dissatisfaction key factors. This fuzzy expert system can consider satisfaction level and the weight of each factor simultaneously to identifying and prioritizing dissatisfaction key factors.

The approach applied in Bandar abbas oil refining company as a one of the biggest companies in Iran. Real evidences showed that transmit requests have increased between employees and they prefer to leave Bandar abbas

and work in another branch of NIOC. This study showed that there are some concerns about healthy subjects such as payback treatment cost process, variety of specialist in treatment center of Mrvarid town and transmit illness to other treatment centers in necessary situations. Also, available income compare to living costs is not balanced and it is one of the important problems. Total satisfaction calculated %54.4 that shows it is not in good level and top management should remove these dissatisfaction key factors to improve satisfaction level.

In cases where there are many factors and employees, the investigation time is increased and data analysis may feel impatient. Interactive design using the computer aid system can be used and the above disadvantage may be improved. Otherwise, when there are many factors, applying AHP method would be difficult, because AHP is based on pairwise comparison and the number of comparison will increase. Using employee's opinions to estimate factor's weight by questionnaire or another methods instead of AHP can explore in the future.

In this study, using the membership function to measure the linguistic variables to achieve better result, which can fairly and exactly reflects the quality of human resource management system. Therefore, the fuzzy logic, thinking and results of the fuzzy approach are better than the traditional statistic approach.

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